

EUROPEAN COOPERATION
IN SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY

CA15104 TD(19)09001
Dublin, Ireland
January 16-18, 2019

EURO-COST

SOURCE: Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC)
Castelldefels, Spain.

Learning Approaches to Beam Selection for Hybrid Analog Beamforming

Carles Antón-Haro (CTTC/iCERCA), Xavier Mestre (CTTC/iCERCA)

Carles Antón-Haro
Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Parc Mediterrani de la Tecnologia (PMT) – Building B6
Carl Frierich Gauss, 7
08860 Castelldefels (SPAIN)
Phone: + 34-93-645.29.00
Fax: + 34-93-645.29.01
Email: carles.anton@cttc.es

Learning Approaches to Beam Selection for Hybrid Analog Beamforming

Carles Antón-Haro and Xavier Mestre

Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/iCERCA)
Parc Mediterrani de la Tecnologia (PMT). Av Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, Building B6
08860 Castelfelers (SPAIN)
{carles.anton,xavier.mestre}@cttc.es

Abstract—This paper investigates the applicability of deep and machine learning techniques to perform beam selection in the uplink of a mmWave communication system. Specifically, we consider a hybrid beamforming setup comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) network followed by a zero-forcing baseband processing block. The goal is to select the optimal configuration for the ABF network based on the estimated angles-of-arrival (AoAs) and received powers. To that aim, we consider three machine/deep learning schemes: k-nearest neighbors (kNN), support vector classifiers (SVC), and the multilayer perceptron (MLP). We conduct an extensive performance evaluation to assess the impact of using the Capon or MUSIC methods to estimate the AoAs and powers, the size of the training dataset, the number of beamformers in the codebook, their beamwidth, or the number of active users. Computer simulations reveal that performance, in terms of classification accuracy and sum-rate, is very close to that achievable via exhaustive search.

I. INTRODUCTION

To date, the application of ML/DL techniques to communication problems has been mostly in the area of wireless network optimization [1]. Authors have tackled a number of problems like intelligent resource management, cell association, selection of radio access technologies, or spectrum management, to name a few. In contrast, there has been very limited progress towards the use of ML/DL techniques for problems and functionalities related with the physical layer (PHY) of communication systems (e.g., coding, modulation, detection, equalization, pre-coding). For this reason, some authors [2] have started investigating how autoencoders can be used to model an end-to-end communication system comprising the encoding, channel and decoding blocks, for MIMO point-to-point and interference channels. The adoption of feedforward deep neural networks for joint channel estimation and data detection under an MMSE criterion is addressed in [3]. Other research works include the adoption of convolutional neural networks (CNN) to carry out sensing, compression and recovery of channel state information (CSI) in the feedback channel of massive MIMO systems [4]; the use of support vector classifiers (SVC) to perform antenna [5] or beam selection [6], or the exploitation of CNNs for modulation classification tasks [2].

This work is partly supported by the European Commission through the Inclusive Radio Communications (IRACON) COST action.

The shift towards communications in mmWave bands makes it feasible to implement transceivers with many more antenna elements. In order to keep hardware cost and computational complexity at reasonable levels, a number of techniques have been proposed. Hybrid beamforming, for instance, can be used to partition beamforming into the digital and analog (RF) domains and, by doing so, reduce the number of RF chains needed in the base station. In this context, the development of efficient (analog) beam selection techniques has become a hot research area. In [7], for instance, the authors present an iterative scheme where, in each iteration, the beam that contributes less to the sum-rate of a multi-user MIMO system is eliminated. In [8], instead, the proposed low-complexity beam selection algorithm exploits the fact that an approximation of the sum-rate can be computed out of the elements of the effective channel matrix at the output of the analog beamforming (ABF) block. The approximation is near optimal in the high-SNR regime.

The applicability of ML techniques to beam selection tasks is investigated in [6]. Specifically, the authors model beam selection (in a hybrid receiver architecture with a ZF block) as an instance of a multi-class classification problem, and attempt to solve it with a support vector classifier (SVC). To that aim, the availability of the actual angle-of-arrival (AoA) and amplitude information for each scattering path is assumed. Complementarily, in [9] Heath *et al* investigate the performance of several ML schemes (SVC, Adaboost, Decision trees, Random forests) but also that of deep neural networks (DNN) and reinforcement learning for beam pair selection in vehicle-to-infrastructure settings. The proposed methods leverage on the error-free positioning information (vehicle locations) supplied by an *external* entity.

In this paper, we investigate the applicability of deep and machine learning techniques to perform analog beam selection in the uplink of a multi-user MIMO mmWave communication system. As in [6], [7], [10], we adopt a hybrid beamforming architecture with an analog beamforming (ABF) network and a ZF baseband processing block. The proposed ML/DL schemes leverage on partial CSI, namely, the angles-of-arrival (AoA) and received powers but, unlike [6], [9], such information is not assumed to be known or externally supplied. Instead, it is *estimated* by the same system via a Capon (minimum variance) or, differently from [11], MUSIC spectral estimation [12]. The

proposed ML/DL schemes include support vector classifiers like in [6], [9], but we also consider other schemes like k -nearest neighbors (that was used in [5] for transmit antenna selection) or the multi-layer perceptron (MLP). Unlike in many previous works, we propose to use a codebook of analog beamformers with adjustable beamwidth (rather than phased-arrays or DFT-based codebooks) as a means to enhance/guarantee system performance. Differently from our previous work [11], the focus here is on performing an extensive performance evaluation of the proposed ML/DL schemes. Specifically, we investigate the impact of CSI estimates (namely, estimated AoAs and powers), the actual CSI estimation method (Capon, MUSIC), the size of the training dataset, the total number of analog beamformers in the codebook, the beamwidth of such beamformers and, finally, the number of active users.

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODEL

Consider the uplink of a multi-user SIMO system operating in the mm-Wave band. As shown in Fig. 1, the base station (BS) is equipped with N_{BS} antennas and serves K mobile terminals. The BS adopts a hybrid beamforming architecture, comprising an analog beamforming (ABF) and a digital/baseband (BBF) beamforming block. The former performs a spatial pre-filtering of the received signal, whereas the latter is aimed at removing the remaining inter-user interference. The ABF network provides full connectivity among the set of receive antennas and the N_{RF} radiofrequency chains. The

Fig. 1: System Model.

received signal at the BS after RF and baseband combining can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{z} = \mathbf{W}^H \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}^H \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{n} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{BS}} \times K}$ is the channel matrix, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ denotes the transmit signal, with its elements fulfilling $\mathbb{E}[\|x_k\|^2] = P_k$ for $k = 1 \dots K$; vector $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{BS}} \times 1}$ is zero-mean i.i.d. AWGN noise with variance σ^2 , i.e., $\mathbf{n} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_{N_{\text{BS}}})$; and, finally, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RF}} \times K}$ and $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{BS}} \times N_{\text{RF}}}$ stand for the BBF and ABF matrices, respectively. For the channel, we adopt a geometric model with L scattering paths, which is widely-used in mm-

Wave communications. Consequently, for the channel matrix $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1 \dots \mathbf{h}_K]$, we have that

$$\mathbf{h}_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L\rho_k}} \sum_{i=1}^L \alpha_{k,i} \mathbf{a}_{\text{BS}}(\theta_{k,i}^{\text{BS}}), \quad (2)$$

where $\alpha_{k,i}$ is the complex gain of the i -th path with $\mathbb{E}[\|\alpha_{k,i}\|] = 1$, ρ_k is the path-loss between the BS and the k -th user, and $\theta_{k,i}^{\text{BS}} \in [-\pi/2, \dots, \pi/2]$ denotes the AoA of the i -th path of user k . Vector $\mathbf{a}_{\text{BS}}(\theta_{k,i}^{\text{BS}})$ is the response for a uniform linear array at the BS:

$$\mathbf{a}_{\text{BS}}(\theta_{k,i}^{\text{BS}}) = \left[1, e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d \sin(\theta_{k,i}^{\text{BS}})}, \dots, e^{j(N_{\text{BS}}-1)\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d \sin(\theta_{k,i}^{\text{BS}})} \right] \quad (3)$$

where λ is the signal wavelength, and d is the distance between antenna elements (in the sequel, we assume $d = 0.5\lambda$).

III. ANALOG AND DIGITAL BEAMFORMING STRATEGIES

Let \mathcal{B} denote a codebook of $B = |\mathcal{B}|$ different configurations of the ABF network (referred to, in the sequel, as *analog beamformers*):

$$\mathcal{B} = \{\mathbf{B}_1, \dots, \mathbf{B}_{|\mathcal{B}|}\} \quad (4)$$

with $\mathbf{B}_i \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{BS}} \times N_{\text{RF}}}$ denoting each of those analog beams. Since we are interested in performing a spatial pre-filtering, we let the j -th column vector $\mathbf{b}_{i,j}$ in $\mathbf{B}_i = [\mathbf{b}_{i,1}, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{i,N_{\text{RF}}}]$ point at a different direction θ_d out of a set of D AoAs evenly spaced in $[-\pi/2 \dots \pi/2]$. And, as a design decision, we set D in such a way that the resulting number of elements (analog beamformers) in the codebook $B = \binom{D}{N_{\text{RF}}}$ is larger than or equal to N_{BS} .

A straightforward choice for $\mathbf{b}_{i,j} = \mathbf{b}_{i,j}(\theta_d)$ would be phased arrays, namely,

$$\mathbf{s}(\theta_d) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{\text{BS}}}} \left[1, e^{j\frac{\pi}{\sin}(\theta_d)}, \dots, e^{j(N_{\text{BS}}-1)\pi \sin(\theta_d)} \right] \quad (5)$$

For large N_{BS} , however, the resulting beams become too narrow (to recall, their 3 dB beamwidth is $2/N_{\text{BS}}$). As discussed in [11] (and further analyzed in the Section VI), this yields a poor classification performance and, thus, must be avoided. Instead, we let \mathbf{b} (sub-indices i, j have been dropped, for brevity) be the solution to the following optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{b}}{\text{maximize}} && \int_{\theta_d - \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}}^{\theta_d + \frac{\Delta\theta}{2}} \mathbf{b}^H \mathbf{s}(\theta) \mathbf{s}^H(\theta) \mathbf{b} d\theta \\ & \text{subject to} && \|\mathbf{b}\|^2 = 1. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}$ is a design parameter related with the interval around θ_d where we want to *broaden* the beam. This problem can be easily solved in closed-form as discussed in [12].

However, the distribution of occurrences for such set of analog beamformers is not uniform in practice. Even if the AoAs of the various users are indeed uniformly distributed in $[-\pi/2, \dots, \pi/2]$ the actual selection depends on the interplay of the AoAs of the user of interest *and* the interferers (and their number). Restricting the search to the $B_{\text{sub}} \leq B$ most

popular elements¹ in the entire codebook, has the beneficial effects of rendering (i) the selection process less complex (fewer choices); and (ii) the dimension of the resulting models lower (and, thus, easier to fit). However, this strategy has an impact on system performance (see Section VI ahead).

For baseband (digital) beamforming, we adopt a zero-forcing ZF scheme, as e.g., in [6]. By defining the effective channel matrix as the product of the actual channel and the analog beamforming matrix, namely, $\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}} = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H}$, the BBF matrix reads:

$$\mathbf{W} = (\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}^H \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}})^{-1} \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}^H. \quad (7)$$

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Our goal is to select the analog beamformer from the B -element codebook \mathcal{B} such that the sum rate at the output of the BBF block is maximized. From the system model presented in the preceding section, the sum rate can be expressed as:

$$R(b) = \sum_{k=1}^K \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{P_k / \rho_k}{\sigma^2 [(\mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}(b)^H \mathbf{H}_{\text{eff}}(b))^{-1}]_{kk}} \right)$$

where $[\mathbf{A}]_{kk}$ denotes the k -th element in the diagonal of matrix \mathbf{A} , and where the dependency of \mathbf{H}_{eff} on the codebook index b has been made explicit.

In order to select the optimal beamformer (and avoid exhaustive searches over the codebook elements), one should leverage on \mathbf{H} as channel state information. However, under the assumption of a hybrid beamforming architecture, \mathbf{H} cannot be readily estimated in the digital domain (since the number of RF chains, N_{RF} , is smaller than the number of antennas, N_{BS}). Alternatively, we propose to use some sufficient statistic derived from \mathbf{H} . In particular, we investigate whether the AoA and received power for each user terminal can be exploited. From all the above, the selection process can be modeled as a classification problem that, in turn, can be effectively solved with machine and deep learning tools (which are presented in Section V).

In order to estimate the set of AoAs and received powers (see above), we resort to the Capon (i.e., minimum variance) or MUSIC (MUltiple SIgnal Classifier) power spectral estimators [12]. The latter exhibits a much higher spatial resolution and, thus, it can alleviate the problems (i.e., poor classification accuracy with estimated AoAs) encountered in our previous work [11]. To estimate AoAs and powers, however, we can only use the $N_{\text{RF}} \times 1$ baseband signal $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}^H \mathbf{n}$, that is, a *filtered* version of the received signal *after* ABF and analog to digital conversion (to recall, the received signal itself lies in the RF domain).

V. DATA-DRIVEN ANALOG BEAM SELECTION

The task of selecting the optimal analog beamformer can be modeled as a supervised learning problem. Specifically it can be cast into a multi-class classification task where:

¹To identify the most popular subset of ABFs, it suffices to generate a number of examples of the scenario under consideration.

- The input is given by the set of estimated AoAs and received powers for all active users, namely, $\mathbf{t} = [\theta_1, \dots, \theta_K, P_1^r, \dots, P_K^r]$. The number of active users K is assumed to be known.
- The output is an index to the element (beamformer) in the codebook, $b \in [1, \dots, B]$, yielding the highest sum rate after ZF.

The training set comprises a total of M examples \mathbf{t}_m stacked in a training matrix $\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{t}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{t}_M^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 2K}$ and a class label vector $\mathbf{c} = [c_1, \dots, c_M]^T \in \mathbb{N}^{M \times 1}$ with the corresponding outputs. To avoid significant bias in the training, features are normalized prior to their use by the learning schemes, namely, $t_{ij} \leftarrow (t_{ij} - E_i t_{ij}) / (\max_i [t_{ij}] - \min_i [t_{ij}])$.

A. Machine Learning Schemes

The so-called k -Nearest Neighbors (kNN) scheme is one of the simplest ML-based classification methods. For a new example \mathbf{t} , the kNN classifier finds the k nearest entries (here, in Euclidean terms) in the training set \mathbf{T} . Then kNN declares the class label for the new example \mathbf{t} based on a (possibly weighted) majority of the nearest neighbors' labels. The only hyper-parameter of the algorithm is G (typically, an odd number, to avoid ambiguity), the number of nearest neighbors to find.

We will also consider a Support Vector Classifier (SVC). For a multi-class classification problems (like ours), SVCs need to solve B binary classification problems. Each of them, identifies one category vs. the other categories (i.e. one-vs.-rest approach). Specifically, during the training phase, binary SVCs fit a separating hyperplane with optimal geometric margin (i.e. maximum distance to the closest elements in each of the two classes). Next, in the test phase, those hyperplanes are used to decide in which region (i.e., class, beamformer index) the new example \mathbf{t} lies. Since our problem is not linearly separable [11], we introduce a Gaussian (radial-based) kernel function to transform the input data. This is equivalent to transforming hyperplanes into more general boundaries. For this kernel in particular, the hyperparameters here are σ_k , the variance of the Gaussian kernel; and, C , a penalty parameter aimed to balance bias and overfitting (see [13] for details).

B. Deep Learning Scheme

Feedforward deep neural networks (DNN) like the multi-layer perceptron (MLP) can be regarded as universal function approximators. Our L -layer MLP consists of: one input layer with $2K$ elements (AoAs, received powers), one output layer with B neurons (the number of elements in the codebook), and $L - 2$ hidden layers with N_l ; $l = 2, \dots, L - 1$ neurons each. This MLP defines a mapping $f(\mathbf{t}, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2K} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^B$ of an input vector \mathbf{t} onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L iterative processing steps:

$$\mathbf{r}_l = f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (8)$$

where $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends, on the one hand, on the output from the previous layer and, on the other, on the

parameter set of that layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model (see below for details). The l -th layer is said to be *dense* if $f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l)$ is of the form

$$f_l(\mathbf{r}_{l-1}; \phi_l) = \sigma(\mathbf{W}_l \mathbf{r}_{l-1} + \mathbf{b}) \quad (9)$$

with $\mathbf{W}_l \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l \times N_{l-1}}$ and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ denoting a matrix of weights and a bias vector, respectively; and $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a (typically non-linear) activation function. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers. On the contrary, a Softmax activation function is used at the output layer, so that the probability for each beamformer can be effectively computed. Further, each hidden layer is followed by a dropout layer in order to avoid overfitting when using the training set. In the training phase, the parameter set in each layer, i.e., $\phi_l = [\mathbf{W}_l, \mathbf{b}_l]$, is adjusted via the so-called stochastic adaptive gradient descent algorithm (Adagrad, [14]) and backpropagation [13]. The goal is to minimize the categorical cross entropy (i.e., maximize classification accuracy).

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Unless otherwise stated, the system scenario comprises one BS equipped with $N_{\text{BS}} = 16$ receive antennas and $N_{\text{RF}} = 6$ RF chains; and a total of $K = 4$ active users. We consider uplink channels with a single scattering path (i.e., $L = 1$), same transmit power $P_k = P$ for all k and (possibly) different path-losses for the various users. The number of examples in the training and test sets was set to $M = 3000$ and $M_{\text{test}} = 3000$, respectively. The hyper-parameters in each model were optimized via grid search. As for the MLP, the number of layers and neurons in the hidden layers was $L = 5$ and $N_l = 125$, respectively. During training, the dropout rate was set to 20% which sufficed to prevent overfitting.

Computer simulation results are given in terms of classification accuracy and sum-rate (see next subsections). As benchmarks, we include (i) *random* beam selection, with uniform distribution in $\{1, \dots, B\}$; and (ii) *optimal* beam selection, which is accomplished via exhaustive search.

A. Performance with MUSIC vs. Capon Spectral Estimation

First, we analyze the impact of the power spectral estimation strategy on performance. We consider a scenario with fluctuations in the received power of ± 2 dB (e.g., due to imperfect power control and/or different user-to-BS distances). As discussed in Section IV, using a high-resolution spectral estimation technique like MUSIC allows to estimate both AoA and received powers more accurately. This, in turn, results into an enhanced classification accuracy for all the proposed ML/DL approaches, as Figure 2 reveals. The gain is particularly high for the MLP scheme, with classification accuracy boosting from 40% to 75% in the high-SNR regime. In the light of this, hereinafter we will restrict our analysis to a system with MUSIC-based CSI estimation.

Yet classification accuracy is a relevant performance measure, from a communications point of view we are often more interested in sum rates. This is illustrated in Fig. 3. Very interestingly, the sum-rate of the MLP approach (in

Fig. 2: Classification accuracy with the MUSIC (solid) and Capon (dash-dotted) methods. Scenario with estimated CSI (AoAs and received powers) and different received powers ($N_{\text{BS}} = 16$, $N_{\text{RF}} = 6$, $K = 4$, $B = 28$, $D = 8$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$).

combination with MUSIC) is virtually identical to that of optimal beam selection. And this happens despite of the fact that its classification accuracy is approximately 80% (see Fig. 2 above). This is due to the fact that most classification errors occur among adjacent classification regions. These regions, by codebook construction (see Section III) are associated to beamformers with a similar spatial response. And, for a given set of AoAs, they result into similar sum-rates. Only when classification accuracy degrades further, for instance for the kNN and SVC approaches, does the sum-rate loss become noticeable. Nevertheless, for this particular scenario, these two ML schemes still manage to retain some 90% of the achievable sum-rate with optimal beam selection. The fact that the DL approach (MLP) outperforms its ML counterparts (kNN, SVC) comes at a price of a higher computational complexity.

Fig. 3: Percentage of the sum-rate vs. signal-to-noise ratio ($N_{\text{BS}} = 16$, $N_{\text{RF}} = 6$, $K = 4$, $\text{SNR} = 20\text{dB}$, $B = 28$, $B_{\text{sub}} = 16$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 8$, MUSIC estimator).

Fig. 4: Classification accuracy vs. number of examples in the training set ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 6$, $K = 4$, $SNR = 20\text{dB}$, $B = 28$, $B_{sub} = 16$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 8$, MUSIC estimator).

B. Impact of training dataset and codebook size

The size of the training dataset has a direct impact in terms of complexity vs. performance trade-offs, and over/underfitting vs. generalization capabilities. Figure 4 below depicts classification performance as a function of the number of examples in the training dataset (M). For small M , the performance exhibited by all the ML/DL approaches is low due to underfitting. In this region, however, classification accuracy increases rapidly with M and, to a large extent, it stabilizes for $M > 3000$ examples. This holds in particular for the MLP approach. No overfitting problems were observed for the range of dataset sizes of interest (thanks to the use of dropout layers).

One more important aspect to investigate is the impact of the number of elements in the ABF codebook. In terms of classification accuracy, Fig. 5 left, the percentage of correct (optimal) decisions tends to increase for a reduced number of codebook elements: the number of beamformers to choose from is lower and so is the probability of a wrong decision.

As for sum-rate (Fig. 5, right), the analysis is more involved. First, from the optimal selection curve, one realizes that reducing the cardinality of the codebook can only be detrimental: the optimal selection in a smaller codebook is potentially different from that of a larger one. And the selection from a larger codebook is likely to mitigate interference more effectively (the more beamformers, the more diverse interference scenarios can be effectively handled). The sum-rate degradation is particularly noticeable for codebooks with $B_{sub} < 8$ beamformers since such elements are often used.

The impact of errors in the selection of ABFs is better illustrated by the random selection curve. For small B_{sub} , the sum-rate associated to each element in the codebook is lower but the probability of making a wrong selection is lower too. For large B_{sub} , it is just the opposite. This suggests the existence of some value of B_{sub} attaining the best trade-off between the two effects (approximately, $B_{sub} = 8$ in this case).

The proposed ML/DL schemes, of course, are capable of

harnessing the benefits of working with larger codebooks in a more effective manner than a mere random selection. This results in a set of curves which are monotonically increasing with the number of available ABFs (as with optimal selection decisions) but with some performance gap, accounting for the sum-rate penalty associated to incorrect selection decisions. It is worth noting that, again, the gap for the whole range of B_{sub} values is negligible for the MLP scheme. And, even more interestingly, the sum-rate degradation for $B_{sub} \geq N_{BS}$ (with respect to the $B_{sub} = B$ case) is barely noticeable. Hence, in the sequel, we let $B_{sub} = N_{BS}$.

Fig. 5: Performance vs. number of analog beamformers (B_{sub}) in the codebook: classification accuracy (left) and sum-rate (right) ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 6$, $K = 4$, $SNR = 20\text{dB}$, $B = 28$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 8$, MUSIC estimator).

C. Impact of beamwidth and number of active users

In this last part, we investigate the effect of beamwidth on performance. As discussed in previous sections, the classification accuracy associated to phased arrays ($\Delta\theta/2 = 0$, narrow beams) is poor. On the contrary, using non-directional beams (large $\Delta\theta$) is detrimental too: in this case, AoA information is not anymore a sufficient statistic to perform beam selection. Both effects can be clearly observed in Fig. 6 left below. Hence, the optimal classification performance is attained for some intermediate beamwidth values (in this particular scenario, at $\Delta\theta/2 = 4/D$ for MLP and SVC, and $\Delta\theta/2 = 6/D$ for kNN).

Complementarily, Figure 6 (right) illustrates the achievable performance in terms of sum-rate. Here, the impact of beamwidth is two-fold: not only in terms of separability of the decision regions, classification performance and, ultimately, their impact on sum-rate; but also on its interference mitigation capabilities. In other words, the larger the beamwidth, the higher the impact of interferers after the analog (ABF) and digital (BBF) beamforming blocks and, thus, the lower the sum-rate. Due to this, the optimal value of $\Delta\theta/2$ in terms of sum-rate differs from (and is smaller than) that observed for classification accuracy. For the ML and DL schemes, the degradation with respect to optimal beam selection (caused by classification errors) is, in general, small.

Finally, we focus our attention on the number of active users K (Fig. 7). For small K , the communications system

Fig. 6: Performance vs. beamwidth $\Delta\theta/2$: classification accuracy (left) and sum-rate (right) ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 6$, $K = 4$, SNR = 20dB, $B = 28$, $D = 8$, MUSIC estimator).

is noise-limited but the sum-rate is necessarily low due to the limited number of contributors (users) to the aggregated rate. For an increasing number of users, the number of contributors increases but, to start with, the classification accuracy deteriorates. This stems from the fact that the number of inputs to the classification scheme grows linearly in the number of users, this rendering the decision regions and the model to be fit more complex. Further, the system becomes interference-limited, this bringing in an additional source of degradation.

Fig. 7: Sum-rate performance vs. number of users, for SNR = 10dB (dashed lines) and SNR = 20dB (solid lines) ($N_{BS} = 16$, $N_{RF} = 6$, $K = 4$, $B = 28$, $B_{sub} = 16$, $\Delta\theta/2 = 3/D$, $D = 8$, MUSIC estimator).

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have investigated how angle-of-arrival information can be exploited by deep-/machine-learning approaches to perform beam selection in a hybrid beamforming setup. Specifically, we have posed the beam selection task as a multi-class classification problem and solved it via two machine-learning (ML) approaches: k-nearest neighbors, support vector classifiers; and one deep learning approach: the multilayer perceptron. We have also designed a new

beamformer set with larger and configurable beamwidth which is tailored to the beam selection task.

Computer simulation results reveal that using MUSIC (vs. Capon power spectral estimation) results in an enhanced classification accuracy in particular for the MLP scheme (close to 80%). As a result, its sum-rate is virtually identical to that of optimal beam selection since most classification errors occur among adjacent regions. As for the ML schemes, they retain some 90% of the sum-rate with optimal beam selection. As for the size of the training dataset, we found out that classification performance saturates when the number of examples reaches 3000. Concerning the number of analog beamformers, we considered a scenario with a total of $B = 28$ initial elements in the codebook. We learnt that, if the selection is restricted to the subset of $B_{subset} = 16$ most popular beamformers (or more), the sum-rate remains unchanged. On the contrary, for subsets of $B_{subset} \geq 8$ elements, performance degrades very rapidly. Besides, we realized that there exists an optimal value for the beamwidth of analog beamformers. This makes it possible to strike the optimal balance between too narrow beams (i.e., in phased arrays) exhibiting poor classification accuracy/sum-rate; and too broad/non-directional ones for which the angles or arrival are not a sufficient statistic to perform classification. Concerning the number of active users, a similar behaviour (convex, with some optimal value) was observed.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Jiang, H. Zhang, Y. Ren, Z. Han, K. C. Chen, and L. Hanzo, "Machine learning paradigms for next-generation wireless networks," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 98–105, April 2017.
- [2] T. O'Shea and J. Hoydis, "An introduction to deep learning for the physical layer," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 563–575, Dec 2017.
- [3] H. Ye, G. Y. Li, and B. H. Juang, "Power of deep learning for channel estimation and signal detection in ofdm systems," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 114–117, Feb 2018.
- [4] C. Wen, W. Shih, and S. Jin, "Deep learning for massive mimo csi feedback," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, pp. 1–1, 2018.
- [5] J. Joung, "Machine learning-based antenna selection in wireless communications," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 20, no. 11, pp. 2241–2244, Nov 2016.
- [6] Y. Long, Z. Chen, J. Fang, and C. Tellambura, "Data-driven based analog beam selection for hybrid beamforming under mm-wave channels," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, pp. 1–1, 2018.
- [7] R. Pal, K. V. Srinivas, and A. K. Chaitanya, "A beam selection algorithm for millimeter-wave multi-user mimo systems," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 852–855, April 2018.
- [8] Y. Niu, Z. Feng, Y. Li, Z. Zhong, and D. Wu, "Low complexity and near-optimal beam selection for millimeter wave mimo systems," in *2017 13th International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC)*, June 2017, pp. 634–639.
- [9] A. Klautau, P. Batista, N. Gonzalez-Prelcic, Y. Wang, and R. Heath, "5G MIMO data for machine learning: Application to beam selection using deep learning," in *Proceedings of the Information Theory and Applications Workshop 2018*, Feb. 2018.
- [10] S. Qiu, K. Luo, and T. Jiang, "Beam selection for mmwave massive mimo systems under hybrid transceiver architecture," *IEEE Communications Letters*, pp. 1–1, 2018.
- [11] C. Antón-Haro and X. Mestre, "On the applicability of machine and deep learning techniques for beam selection in hybrid beamforming architectures with partial CSI," in *Submitted to IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*, April 2019.
- [12] H. L. V. Trees, *Optimum Array Processing: Part IV of Detection, Estimation, and Modulation Theory*, 2002.
- [13] A. Smola and S. Vishwanathan, *Introduction to Machine Learning*, 2008.

- [14] J. Duchi, E. Hazan, and Y. Singer, "Adaptive subgradient methods for online learning and stochastic optimization," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*.